

CHEMISTRY SCIENCES

THERMODYNAMIC PROPERTIES OF DERIVATIVES OF 2-METHYL-5-PHENYL-1H-1H-PYRROLE-3-CARBOXYLIC ACIDS IN THE CONDENSED STATE

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Abstract

According to the Paal–Knorr reaction, 1-cyclohexyl-2-methyl-5-phenyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid and 2-methyl-5-phenyl-1-(4-tolyl)-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid were synthesized. The main stages of the synthesis were described, and the yields of the target products were determined. The structures of the synthesized compounds were confirmed by nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy, and the corresponding NMR spectra are reported.

The potential biological activity of the compounds was evaluated using the PLATO r36 web application. The changes in the internal energy of combustion, as well as the enthalpies of combustion and formation of the synthesized compounds in the condensed state, were experimentally determined using precision calorimetric equipment. Based on the experimental data obtained, the thermodynamic parameters were recalculated to the standard temperature of 298.15 K.

Keywords: enthalpy of combustion; enthalpy of formation; 1-cyclohexyl-2-methyl-5-phenyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid; 2-methyl-5-phenyl-1-(4-tolyl)-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid.

Introduction

The development of the pharmaceutical market in the modern world is occurring at an exceptionally rapid pace. New compounds capable of exhibiting diverse biological activities are synthesized daily, including those containing heterocyclic fragments with a nitrogen atom in their structure [1–2]. It is well known that heterocyclic compounds play a crucial role in the metabolic processes of all living cells, while pharmacologically active heterocyclic systems find wide application in clinical practice [3].

One of the promising directions in contemporary pharmaceutical research is the imitation of structurally natural fragments to expand the range of action of medicinal agents. In particular, the introduction of various substituents into molecules allows significant modification of their physicochemical and biological properties, such as lipophilicity, polarity, water solubility, and selectivity, often achieved through bioisosteric replacements [4].

Among nitrogen-containing heterocyclic systems, pyrrole occupies a special place. This heterocycle is a component of numerous biologically active compounds of plant and animal origin. In particular, the pyrrole fragment is part of important biomolecules such as the enzyme catalase, the mold pigment prodigiosin, the bile pigment bilirubin, plant cell chlorophyll, heme, and vitamin B₁₂ in animal cells [5–6].

Compounds containing a pyrrole fragment in their structure have demonstrated significant biological activity. They are widely used as fungicidal, antibacterial, antifungal, anti-inflammatory,

antipyretic, antitumor, and antihyperlipidemic agents [5, 7–9]. In addition, such compounds are employed as therapeutically active substances [10], as well as cholesterol-lowering and antioxidant agents [11].

Given the high potential of pyrrole-containing compounds as components of medicinal drugs, this study focuses on the synthesis and investigation of the biological activity of 1-cyclohexyl-2-methyl-5-phenyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid and 2-methyl-5-phenyl-1-(4-tolyl)-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid. The absence of basic thermodynamic parameters for these compounds in the literature, particularly the enthalpies of combustion and formation, necessitated their experimental determination within the framework of this research.

The obtained thermodynamic characteristics will allow optimization of the synthesis, processing, transportation, and storage processes of the studied substances. Furthermore, if necessary, the information on heat-generating capacity can be utilized during the disposal of these compounds by combustion in boilers, with subsequent recovery of released energy in heat exchange processes. This approach represents one of the simplest and most environmentally reasonable methods for the disposal of pharmaceutical compounds containing carbon, hydrogen, oxygen, and nitrogen atoms [12].

The aim of the study:

The aim of this study is to determine the main thermodynamic parameters of 1-cyclohexyl-2-methyl-5-phenyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid and 2-methyl-5-

phenyl-1-(4-tolyl)-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid. Using the bomb calorimetry method, the combustion energy of the studied acids will be measured, and based on these data, the standard enthalpies of combustion and formation in the condensed state will be calculated. The obtained values of the phase transition parameters

will then be recalculated to the commonly accepted temperature of 298.15 K.

Experimental

The synthesis of 2-methyl-5-phenyl-1*R*-1*H*-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acids was carried out according to the reaction scheme shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1. Synthesis of 2-methyl-5-phenyl-1*R*-1*H*-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid derivatives.

The synthesis was performed in two stages:

Stage 1. A suspension of metallic sodium (0.03 mol), ground in 40 mL of toluene, was gradually treated with ethyl acetoacetate (0.044 mol) under cooling and vigorous stirring. The reaction mixture was maintained with stirring at room temperature for three days. After cooling to 283.15 K, phenacyl bromide (0.03 mol) was added to the mixture, which was stirred for 1 hour at this temperature, and then for an additional 24 hours at room temperature.

Upon completion of the reaction, the solid sodium bromide residues were removed by filtration, and the organic solvent (toluene) was evaporated under reduced pressure (30 mmHg). The resulting residue was distilled under vacuum; the boiling point was 448–450 K at 2 mmHg. As a result, ethyl 2-acetyl-4-oxo-4-phenylbutanoate (3) was obtained in a yield of 6.35 g (86%).

Stage 2. A quantity of 5.00 g (0.02 mol) of ethyl 2-acetyl-4-oxo-4-phenylbutanoate (3) was dissolved in 30 mL of cooled acetic acid, after which 0.02 mol of the corresponding amine was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2.5 hours. After cooling, the mixture was diluted with 100 mL of water, and the formed viscous oils were extracted with dichloromethane. The organic phase was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate for 2 hours.

After removal of the solvent, an aqueous solution of potassium hydroxide (2.24 g, 0.04 mol) in 20 mL of ethanol was added to the crude ester (3). The mixture was heated for 15 minutes, cooled to room temperature, and then 50 mL of water was added. The solution was acidified with diluted hydrochloric acid (1:1), yielding the target acids (5), which were purified by recrystallization from ethanol.

The structures of the synthesized acids were analyzed and confirmed by ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectroscopy using a Bruker Avance 500 spectrometer.

1-cyclohexyl-2-methyl-5-phenyl-1*H*-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid: Yield 4.4 g (77 %), m. p. 227–228 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃), δ, m.ч.: 11.66 (br.s, 1H), 7.43 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 2H), 7.37 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 1H), 7.30 (d, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 2H), 6.27 (s, 1H), 3.98 (tt, *J* = 12.7, 3.6 Hz, 1H), 2.66 (s, 3H), 2.03 – 1.46 (m, 8H), 1.16 – 1.08 (m, 2H). ¹³C NMR (151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 166.23, 135.47, 133.49, 133.26, 129.61, 128.36, 127.61, 112.37, 110.13, 57.02, 31.69, 25.91, 24.73, 12.80. ИЧ-спектр (ATR см⁻¹): 2932,29, 2858,13, 2587,15, 1655,83, 1604,49, 1563,13, 1527,47, 1480,41, 1441,90, 1430,49, 1390,56, 1342,07, 1259,34, 1199,44, 1149,53, 1071,08, 1028,30, 954,14, 892,81, 851,45, 821,50, 778,71, 714,53, 707,40, 686,01, 653,20, 616,12, 544,81, 494,90, 462,09, 426,44.

2-methyl-5-phenyl-1-(4-tolyl)-1*H*-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid: Yield 4.9 g (83 %), m. p. 229–230 °C. ¹H ЯМР (500 MHz, CDCl₃), δ, м.ч.: 11.93 (br.s, 1H), 7.25 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 2H), 7.17 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 2H), 7.14 – 7.08 (m, 3H), 7.05 (d, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 2H), 6.65 (s, 1H), 2.33 (s, 3H), 2.28 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 166.07, 137.90, 137.45, 135.07, 133.12, 132.12, 129.83, 128.19, 128.14, 127.65, 126.47, 112.70, 109.88, 20.65, 12.15. ИЧ-спектр (ATR см⁻¹): 2849,57, 2591,43, 1655,83, 1600,21, 1556,00, 1514,64, 1470,42, 1430,49, 1399,11, 1377,72, 1282,16, 1267,90, 1243,66, 1155,23, 1071,08, 1043,99, 1022,59, 948,43, 917,05, 830,06, 802,96, 782,99, 760,17, 727,37, 711,68, 695,99, 668,89, 644,65, 626,11, 616,12, 521,99, 462,09, 413,60.

The results obtained using the web-based PLATO r36 program are summarized in Table 1 [13]

Predicted Biological Activity of 2-Methyl-5-phenyl-1R-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic Acid Derivatives			
Target	Parameter	Activity	Therapeutic Effect
1-cyclohexyl-2-methyl-5-phenyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid			
RNA-dependent RNA polymerase	IC50	827 nM	Hepatitis C
Estrogen receptor	IC50	251 nM	Breast cancer
Cannabinoid receptor 1/2	Ki	87.5–302 nM	Pain, inflammation
Poly[ADP-ribose] polymerase 1	IC50	108 nM	Cancer
Tyrosine-protein kinase 1/2	Ki	10.2–48.2 nM	Autoimmune diseases
Nonstructural protein	IC50	50.1 nM	Hepatitis C therapy
2-methyl-5-phenyl-1-(4-tolyl)-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid			
D2 dopamine receptor	IC50	211 nM	Schizophrenia
Sodium-dependent serotonin transporter	IC50	113 nM	Depression
Sodium-dependent dopamine transporter	IC50	269 nM	Parkinson's disease, ADHD
Cyclin-dependent kinase 1–5	IC50	360–471 nM	Cancer
5-Hydroxytryptamine receptor	Ki	55.3 nM	Mental disorders
Dipeptidyl peptidase	IC50	77.3 nM	Type 2 diabetes

A comparative analysis of the predicted biological activity results obtained using the web-based PLATO r36 platform confirms the presence of consistent patterns in the identification of potential biological targets for the studied compounds, as well as the prospects for investigating the synthesized substances as components of pharmaceutical drugs.

Combustion calorimetry studies were conducted following the methodology described in [14]. The measurement of the combustion energy of the carboxylic acids was performed using a precision B-08-MA calorimeter with an isothermal jacket (± 0.003 K) and a static calorimetric bomb. According to the procedures outlined in [15], the energy equivalent of the calorimetric setup was determined to be $W = 10343.0 \pm 6.8$ J/V. This value was established using standard benzoic acid with a main component content of 99.995 ± 0.01 mol %, with a relative error of ± 0.06 %.

Under normal conditions, the studied acids exist in the solid state. Portions of the acids were pressed into tablets using a die, tied with cotton thread, placed in a platinum cup, and positioned inside the calorimetric bomb. One milliliter of distilled water was added to the bomb. Ignition of the samples was initiated by discharging capacitors through a nichrome wire, which in turn ignited the cotton thread. The initial oxygen pressure in the calorimetric bomb, previously purified from combustible impurities, carbon dioxide, and water vapor, was 30 atm. The temperature at the beginning of all experiments was 298.15 K.

Upon completion of each combustion experiment, a quantitative analysis of the combustion by-products was performed to detect carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, soot, and nitric acid. Gas analysis of the formed carbon dioxide was carried out using the Rossini method [16] with an accuracy of $\pm 2 \cdot 10^{-4}$ g. Additionally, in selected experiments, the carbon monoxide content was determined using indicator tubes

with an accuracy of $\pm 5 \cdot 10^{-6}$ g. The reliability of the applied gas analysis was confirmed through a series of combustion experiments with standard benzoic acid.

The analysis of nitric acid formed in the calorimetric bomb was performed by titration with a 0.1 N potassium hydroxide solution. The amount of soot deposited on the walls of the platinum cup after sample combustion was determined by weighing with an accuracy of $\pm 5 \cdot 10^{-6}$ g.

Results and discussion

The calculation of the combustion energy $\Delta_c U$ of the studied acid under the combustion process conditions was carried out according to equation (1):

$$-\Delta_c U = \frac{W \cdot \Delta T - Q_{fuser} - Q_{HNO_3} + Q_{carb}}{m_{comp}} \quad (1)$$

where W is the energy equivalent of the calorimetric system, J/V; ΔT is true temperature increase in a calorimetric experiment; m_{comp} is the mass of the substance that burned during the experiment, g; Q_{fuser} , Q_{HNO_3} and Q_{carb} is the amount of heat released during the combustion of cotton thread (16704.2 J/g), the formation of nitric acid solution (59 J/g) and the formation of soot (32800 J/g), respectively [15].

Tables 2 and 3 present the data of the experimental determination of the combustion energies of the acids according to Equation (1), as well as the combustion completeness (%). The values of combustion completeness are expressed as the ratio of the amount of carbon dioxide determined from the gas analysis to the amount of carbon dioxide calculated from the stoichiometric equations (2–3) of the acid combustion reaction:

Table 2

Experimental determination of the combustion energy of 1-cyclohexyl-2-methyl-5-phenyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid

m_{comp} , g	ΔT , V	Q_{fuser} , J	Q_{HNO_3} , J	Q_{carb} , J	$-\Delta_c U$, J/g	Combustion completeness, %
0,20801	0,68625	95,4	3,5	27,1	33778	99,79
0,24876	0,81530	69,2	6,5	50,2	33797	99,98
0,24596	0,80910	79,8	4,7	32,1	33812	99,95
0,09511	0,31711	82,0	4,1	21,3	33802	99,89
0,19980	0,66217	101,1	5,9	14,8	33817	99,78
0,23313	0,76909	94,3	6,8	29,4	33814	99,62
0,22292	0,73244	79,3	6,5	37,6	33768	99,91
$\Delta_c U = -33798 \pm 16 \text{ J/g}$						

Table 3

Experimental determination of the combustion energy of 2-methyl-5-phenyl-1-(4-tolyl)-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid

m_{comp} , g	ΔT , V	Q_{fuser} , J	Q_{HNO_3} , J	Q_{carb} , J	$-\Delta_c U$, J/g	Combustion completeness, %
0,06875	0,23085	134,5	0,6	6,6	32861	99,77
0,10988	0,36082	122,9	1,8	12,1	32939	99,91
0,09545	0,31312	107,4	1,8	9,3	32883	99,89
0,11511	0,37212	68,9	3,5	13,6	32925	99,72
0,08422	0,27551	86,3	2,7	11,5	32915	99,86
0,10607	0,34467	88,5	2,7	12,8	32870	99,85
0,08897	0,29096	95,2	3,1	15,1	32892	99,79
$\Delta_c U = -32898 \pm 25 \text{ J/g}$						

Taking into account the Washburn correction (π) and the correction for expansion work (ΔnRT) [15], the average combustion energy was used to calculate the standard enthalpy of combustion, $\Delta_c H_{298}^0$. To determine the standard enthalpy of formation, $\Delta_f H_{298}^0$, in the condensed state for the studied acid, the following

formation energies (kJ/mol) were employed: $\text{CO}_2(\text{g}) = 393.51 \pm 0.13$; $\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{l}) = 285.830 \pm 0.040$; $\text{O}_2(\text{g}) = 0$ [17]. Table 4 presents the determined standard combustion energy, the Washburn correction, the expansion work correction, and the calculated standard enthalpies of combustion and formation in the condensed state for the investigated acid.

Table 4

Standardized calorimetry values for combustion of 2-Methyl-5-phenyl-1R-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic Acid Derivatives

Substance	$\Delta_c U_{298,15}^0$	π	ΔnRT	$\Delta_c H_{298,15}^0$, kJ/mol	$\Delta_f H_{298,15}^0$, kJ/mol
1-cyclohexyl-2-methyl-5-phenyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid	-9582,9 \pm 4,6	-5,5	-9,3	-9592,2 \pm 4,6	-492,2 \pm 4,6
2-methyl-5-phenyl-1-(4-tolyl)-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid	-9591,1 \pm 7,3	-6,3	-7,9	-9599,0 \pm 7,3	-307,3 \pm 7,3

The obtained values ($\Delta_c H_{298,15}^0$) for both compounds are close in absolute magnitude, which indicates a similar nature of the energy contribution of the pyrrole core and aromatic substituents to the combustion process.

At the same time, the difference in the values of standard enthalpies of formation ($\Delta_f H_{298,15}^0$) indicates the influence of the nature of the substituent at the nitrogen atom of the pyrrole ring on the thermodynamic stability of the investigated acids in the condensed state. In particular, a more negative value $\Delta_f H_{298,15}^0$ for the 1-cyclohexyl-substituted derivative indicates its

higher thermodynamic stability compared to the 4-tolyl-substituted analogue.

The obtained thermodynamic parameters are important for predicting the energy characteristics of synthesized pyrrole-containing carboxylic acids, optimizing the conditions for their synthesis, storage, and disposal, and can also be used as reference data for further thermochemical and physicochemical studies of compounds of this class.

Conclusions

Based on the research results, a series of fundamental thermodynamic parameters were

established for derivatives of 2-Methyl-5-phenyl-1*H*-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid. The synthesis scheme is presented, and the main stages of the process are described. Their predicted biological activity has been determined.

Using experimental combustion calorimetry, the energy of combustion of the acid was determined, followed by the calculation of standard enthalpies of combustion ($\Delta_c H_{298.15}^0 = -9592,2 \pm 4,6$ kJ/mol; $\Delta_c H_{298.15}^0 = -9599,0 \pm 7,3$ kJ/mol) and formation in the condensed state ($\Delta_f H_{298.15}^0 = -492,2 \pm 4,6$ kJ/mol; $\Delta_f H_{298.15}^0(\text{cr}) = -307,3 \pm 7,3$ kJ/mol).

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